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The Temple of Pudhu Surangudi

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Abstract

The people of Pudhu Surangudi built the temple at a new place named as Pudhu Surangudi in Sattur. They built a temple for the female Goddess 'Bhathrakali' to remove evils, good health and for the betterment of the village people and livelihood. The pooja of the earth was started in the year 1974. The people built the temple after the successful Bhumi Pooja. It took nearly seven years to complete the temple into a big temple. The consecration function was held in his temple in the year 1981. The Goddess 'Bhathrakali' statue was made by the sculptor and priest G.Nagapandian of Srivilliputhur. The priest usually fast for 41 days to design the statute. The people of the Surankudi village and other contributors contributed liberal donations to build the temple. The article studies on the origin and the important facts of the new Surankudi temple.

Keywords: Pudhu Surangudi, Temple, Gods, Festivals.

Introduction

The people of Pudhu Surangudi raised the temple at Pudhu Surangudi village in Sattur. They built a female Goddess to remove evils, good health and betterment of the village.¹ The earth pooja was started in 1974. The people-built temple after the Bhumi Pooja. It took seven years to complete the temple. Consecration function was held in his temple in 1981. Female Goddess statue was made by G. Nagapandian, a priest of Srivilliputhur. The priest usually does fasting for 41 days to design the statute. He made a female Goddess called as 'Bhathrakali'. The people contributed liberal donations. All the community people including Hindu Nadars are worship in the temple.² The interior Gods of the temple are: 1. Lord 'Vinayagar', 2. Lord 'Karuppasamy', 3. Lord 'Bhairava' and 4. Lord 'Nagarja'

Pandhuvarpatti Temples

Pandhuvarpatti people worshipped soil for about 400 years. The soil was taken in Gurumbu. Later they started to worship God. This village people worshipped two Gods. They gods are:³ 1. Kitchchamman and 2. Periyandavar

Kitchchamman Temple

This temple is located at 'Pandhuvarpatti' village in Sattur. It is 8 km away from Sattur. The people worship Goddess 'Kitchchamman'. 'Kitchchamman' is a female Goddess. The deity is belonged to 'Nayakkar' community. It is believed that Goddess had eaten food in the 'Nadar' family house. Hence the Goddess is avoided by 'Naharathar' community.⁴

Interior Gods

There are many interior gods in the 'Kitchchamman' temple. The gods are 1. Lord

Karuppasamy, 2. Lord Periyandavar, 3. Lord Siva, 4. Lord Vishnu, 5. Lord Kitchchamman, 6. Lord Lakshmi and 7. Lord Ganesa.

Periyandavar Temple

Periyandavar was a Saivist. People of 'Pandhuvarpatti' village worshipped him as God. Periyandavar Temple is located at Pandhuvarpatti village in Sattur. The temple priest usually tie a cloth on his mouth during the time of prayer. He sung any many manthras during the prayer time.⁵ People are worshipping the holy-soil as God for more than 480 years. Later people made Periyandavar statue in 1980 and worshipped it. 'Nadar' people started worshipping Periyandavar Temple at 'Pandhuvarpatti' village in Sattur. There are about 1000 persons belonged to Nadar Community worshipping the temple 'Nadars' have been living in Chennai, Coimbatore, Madurai, Tirunelveli and Kanyakumari, They Nadars haven been arriving from several places to 'Pandhuvarpatti' in each and every year of 'Masi' in Tamil month for the celebration of 'Mahasivarathiri' festival.⁶

Kaliamman Temple

Kaliamman temple is located in Sattur. Sattur people have been worshipping 'Kaliamman', a female Goddess. The tamil word Amma denotes mother in English. 'Kali' is a female goddess. Therefore, the people are called her as Kaliamman.⁷ Goddess 'Kaliamman' is sitting on the Lion. She has 4 hands, a spear holds among the one hand of left two hands and she also hold parrot and bow in another left hand. The Goddess in the right leg used to pedal on demon. This image statue looks elegant in the temple.⁸ This temple has one tower in the main entrance. The height of the tower is 105 feet a length of 57 feet and wide of 59 feet. The temple has gold 'Kalasam' which is covering at the top. All the community people of Sattur are worshipping the Goddess 'Kaliamman'. People are celebrating festival in every year in the Tamil month of 'Pankuni' and 'Chittirai'. On this day, the devotees are fond of performing fire walking ceremony in the temple premises.⁹

Festivals and Poojas of Meenakshi Amman Temple

Festivals are celebrated in 'Venkatasalaphi' temple, 'Irukkankudi Mariamman' temple, 'Meenaakshi Amman' temple, 'Karuppasamy' temple and 'Sri Veerapandia Ayyanar' temple in Sattur throughout the year. Some of the most popular festivals of the temples are 'Chithirai' festival, 'Aavanimoola' festival, 'Maasi Mandala' festival and 'Navaraathri' cultural festival. Festivals are most important occasions of the Hindu society which have intimate connection with the temples.¹⁰ Celebration of festival is the integral part of Indian culture. "Woven into the very fabric of Indian life and ethos are fairs and festivals that have come down to us today, spanning hundreds and even thousands of years in our history and culture. Fairs and festivals are not merely events for merry making but have a vastly deeper significance in our lives, connected as they are to our ancient religion and mythology and what is perhaps not so evident, to the changing rhythms of the six seasonal divisions of the year. Festivals are occasions which give full expression to the social and religious instincts of the people. The land granted by the kings for this purpose was known as 'Thiruvilappuram'."¹¹ An important activity in the Madurai temple is celebration of a number of festivals either by the temple or at the instance of the king or devotees. Festivals came into exist from the rites and ceremonies performed by the early people. It unites the people and strengthened the religious belief. According to Sekizhar, a popular Tamil poet, the purpose of

the birth is two. The first one is to feed the monks or ‘sanyais’ and the next one is to witness a temple festival.¹²

Definition of Festivals

Festivals or Feasts are periodically days and seasons set aside by a community for rest from labour, for the observance of sacred celebrations and religious solemnities. These may be joyful occasions or commemorating the lives of heroes. Festivals besides helping to knit together the body politics, stimulated rivalry in music and the drama and this laid the foundation of great aesthetic triumphs.¹³ P.F. Collier stated that “Feasts and Festivals, celebrations, also known as rest days, memorial days, and holy days. Holidays is derived from the Latin word ‘festum’ (bright, rejoicing). A sharp distinction between the two terms cannot be drawn. “A distinction may be made between feasts, as celebrations at which food and drink are served and festivals, which do not include eating and drinking, as a music festival for example. Such a differentiation however, is quite arbitrary. Many ancient festivals included sumptuous banquets.”¹⁴

The new Encyclopedia Britannica states: “Feast, also known as festival, day or period of time set aside to commemorate or ritually celebrate events or time periods (agricultural, religious or socio-cultural) that give meaning and cohesiveness to an individual and his community.¹⁵ The term festival derives from the fact that such days or periods generally originated in religious celebration or ritual commemorations that included social communal meals: ‘feast is the opposite of ‘fast’. Festivals possess educational, social and religious character. In primitive cults having no written records, seasonal recital of mythology at festival time serves the function of transmitting traditional lore within the tribe. Festivals bind a religious group into a unity that transcends family and local ties.¹⁶ “In the anthologies, the term festival ‘(Vila)’ denotes any act of rejoicing and uproar. Even marriage is referred to as *Vatuvai Vila*. It is used in a very general sense, to devote occasion of varying importance from ordinary religious rites such as ‘velanveriyattu’ to grand social functions such as *Venil Vila*. To think of the current usage, even the anniversaries of great men are referred to as *Vila*. Similarly in ancient days, the laying of the hero stone- *Nadukal* – was celebrated in a grand manner an occasion noted for its fervour and festivity. In this context it is worth mentioning that the anniversary or centenary celebrations or erecting of *Nadukal* cannot be considered occasions of despair and desolateness. They fit in as celebrations which are more in the nature of appreciating one’s greatness and chivalry; deserving posterity’s following them, than expressions of dismay.

Considering all these factors, one may safely conclude that a festival in a general sense is an act of gathering of people with feelings of pleasure or pride. Major Festivals are called in Sanskrit as *Brahmotsava* and *Mahotsava* (maha-grand; *ut* high; *sava*-five works of Siva). *Brahmostava* means ‘Major Festival’.¹⁷

Chithirai Festivals

The Chithirai festival is celebrated for 12 days during the Tamil month of ‘Chithirai’ (April in the English calendar) and begins with the flag hoisting on the first day. On the 8th day the coronation of ‘Meenakshi Amman’ takes place. On the 9th day the Goddess is taken out in procession. On the 10th day the Celestial Wedding of Goddess Meenakshi and Lord Sundareshwarar are performed, followed by car festival the next day. ‘Theerthawari’ festival

(Holy Bathing Festival) is celebrated on the 12th day with the Lord and Goddess held in Sattur.¹⁸

Spring Festival

The spring festival celebrated in 'Vaikasi', a Tamil month (May in the English calendar) is hosted for ten days in every year. On the 10th day, milk and mango are offered to the deities. On the day of Moola star, the procession of 63 Nayanmars is conducted in the morning and in the evening time.¹⁹

Oonjal Festival

Oonjal festival is conducted for ten days in 'Aavani' (June in the English calendar) a Tamil month. On the 10th day, the triple fruit Pooja is performed. 'Abhishekams' for Goddess 'Shivakami Amman' and Arulmighu 'Natarajar' is performed on the day of 'Uthiram'. The 'Panchasabha Nataraja Moorthy' is taken out in procession along Sattur streets.²⁰

Aadi mulaikattu Festival

The Aadi Mulaikattu festival is celebrated in the Tamil month of 'Aadi' (July in the English Calendar) for 10 days. The festival is confined only to the Goddess 'Amman', who would be taken out in procession along the Sattur streets. Special recitals of 'Nadaswaram' are usually the highlights of this festival.

Aavani Festival

The Aavani festival is conducted for 18 days during Tamil month of Aavani (August in the English calendar). Six days of the festival is devoted to Arulmighu 'Chandrasekarar' (Lord Siva) and the balance 12 days for the 'Panchamoorthies'. On the 7th day of the festival, Coronation is performed for 'Lord Sundareshwarar' and on the 8th day the horse reins are exchanged. On the 9th day, the episode of Lord Siva carrying soil for earning 'pittu' is enacted while the holy water festival on the occasion of the joining of 'Avittam' and 'Poornami' (Full moon day) is celebrated. On the same night, 'Arulmighu Thirupparankundram Subramaniyar' and 'Thiruvaadhavur Arulmighu Maanickavaasagar' bid farewell. During the festival of Chandrasekarar, procession is taken out along the second corridor of swami shrine.²¹

Navaraathri Festival:

The Navaraathri festival is celebrated for 'Amman' in a grand manner during 'Purattaasi' month. Goddess 'Meenakshi' appears in resplendent dress and bless the devotees at Meenakshi Amman Temple. Kalpa pooja and Lakshaarchana are performed every day for the Goddess Amman at the sanctum. On the 10th day, the Hair washing ceremony is performed. On this day, 'Panchamoorthies' are taken out in the temple premises. On all ten days of the festival, cultural events are hosted in a grand manner. The entire temple complex is bathed in color lamps and the dolls are arranged in a manner befitting the festival occasion.²²

Wedding of Meenakshi with Sundareshwarar

On the tenth day of the 'Chithirai' Festival the Wedding of Goddess Meenakshi with God Sundareshwarar is celebrated. In this festival, both Lord Subrahmanya and Lord Pavalakkanivay Perumal also participate. One Shiva priest takes the role of Lord Sundareshwarar and another in the role of Goddess Meenakshi and exchange garlands. 'Thirumangalyam' is presented to Meenakshi and traditional ceremonies as in any Hindu

marriage are also performed. The accompanying picture shows the grand wedding scene of the Divine couple.²³

Kolaatam Festival

Kolaatam festival is conducted for six days during 'Aipasi' (October in the English calendar) in Tamil month. For five days Goddess 'Amman' is taken out in procession while on the sixth day both Goddess 'Amman' and Lord 'Swamy' are taken out in the procession. On the days of 'Pooram' in this month, the ceremony of hoisting and swinging Meenakshi Amman is performed.²⁴

Kaarthigai Depam Festival

Deepam (lights) festival is conducted for ten days during 'Kaarthigai' in Tamil month (November in the English calendar). Lord 'Swamy' is taken out in procession along the street of Sattur. On the day of the 'Kaarthigai' one lakh earthen lights are lit in this temple. Oil anointing ceremony is conducted for nine days in this month at New Mandapam. 'Arulmigu Meenakshi Amman' is taken out in procession. Competitions are conducted for school and college students and prizes are distributed.²⁵

Float Festival

The float festival is conducted for 12 days during 'Thai' in Tamil month (January in the English Calendar). Lord 'Swamy' and Goddess 'Amman' are taken out in procession around the 'Chithirai' streets. On the 8th day the casting of net festival is held while 'theertham' festival and the pushing of the float is held on the 10th day. On the 11th day, harvesting of sheaves and on the 12th day the float festival is conducted. The Pandya king once was taking a walk in his garden with the queen when he perceived a sweet scent emanating from the garden or blowing hair of his queen. He wanted to know whether this is natural or artificial for which purpose he announced a competition among the poets of his court. Whoever composes a convincing poem on the issue would be rewarded with a purse of 1000 gold coins. He called a staff filled with thousand gold coins to be hung at the gate of the Sangam hall to be claimed by the group who was daily praying to the Lord seeking funds for this wedding ceremony.²⁶

Somasundarar took pity on the devotee's plight and wrote a verse on the subject of the king's doubt gave it to 'Dharumi' and sent him to claim the staff from the king. While all the poets in the Sangam assembly appreciated the verse and had no hesitation in according the prize to him, 'Nakkeerar' the Minister of Assembly objected to its claiming that the verse was faulty in content. 'Dharumi' went back to the Lord and narrated the whole event, on which Lord Somasundarar himself took the form of a poet and debated with 'Nakkeerar' to win the argument and hand over the gold coins to 'Dharumi'. This episode is re-enacted on the fourth day, the 'AavaniMoolam' festival even to this day. The fifty second episode in 'ThiruvilaiyaadalPuraanam' describes this divine sport.²⁷

Summer Spring Festival

The summer spring festival is hosted for nine days during 'Panguni' in Tamil month (March in the English Calendar) at the 'Velli Ambala Mandapam'. Lord 'Swamy' and Goddess Amman are taken in procession in Sattur. On the day of 'Panguni Uthiram', Lord 'Swamy' and Goddess 'Amman' proceed to 'Arulmighu Thiruvaappudayar' temple and bless those who excel in their religious belief by sprinkling 'rasa vaadham'.²⁸

The Chariot Festival

The Chariot Festival is indeed a marvellous event where men and women from all strata of society gleefully participate. This festival is a unique one as there is a case where the Lord not only showers mercy on those who worship him; but makes a journey, seeks his disciples and blesses them. The chariot itself is an attractive piece, placed on a pedestal, something quite similar to it that in which the main deity is seated inside the temple, with the main deity is seated rostrum and a special structure over it. Representations showing the historic significance of the place of worship have been carved on wood on this chariot-a beguiling presentation by itself. This festival happens on the day following Meenakshi-Sundareshwarar's grand marriage function in Madurai. There are two separate chariots, one for Goddess 'Meenakshi Amman' and the other for Lord 'Sundareshwarar' and Piriyaividai (One who is always with the Lord) and these two chariots would go around the Sattur city. The fact that the Chariot went around 'Maasi Streets' ('Veedhi') is perhaps an indication that this festival was held in the Tamil month of 'Maasi'. The chariots of today were built and offered by Vijaya Ranga Chokkanathathe Nayak, the grandson of Rani Mangammal. Details of the Divine sport of Lord Siva ('Thiruvilaiyaadal Puranam') and of 'Sivakami Puranam' are sculpted on the chariot that belonged to Lord 'Sundareshwarar'.²⁹

The Azhagar Festival

Lord Vishnu's sister Goddess 'Parvathi' was given in marriage to Lord Siva and in that manner becomes Lord Siva's brother-in-law. The Puranas give us this information. The 'Azhagar' "Festival is held to portray the significance of 'Sundararaja Peruaman's' formal visit to conduct the marriage of Goddess 'Meenakshi' from 'Azhagar Kovil' with all the attendant paraphernalia specifically brought from the bride's residence at the time of marriage. As he reaches in the Vaipar River, he gets to know that the marriage has been solemnized. The Lord therefore avoids the southern portion and goes back from the northern side. This has been the familiar story attached with this festival. Lord 'Kallazhagar' after making his presence in river Vaigai reaches Madurai, goes to 'Vandiyur' and then reaches 'Thenur Mandapam', the next day, where the Lord grants deliverance from a damnable curse to 'Mandooga Maharishi'. Then Lord 'Kallazhagar' proceeds to 'Karuppasamy' temple and reaches 'Azhagar Kovil.' At the auspicious time when Lord Kallazhagar rises from the river Vaigai, Veera Raghava Perumal of South Maasi street gets to the spot to welcome the Lord. Today, the marriage ceremony of 'Meenakshi-Sundareshwarar', the chariot festival closely associated with it and the rising of Kallazhagar from Vaigai, combine together to form the "ChithiraiThiruvizha" that is being celebrated in a grand manner with a sense of joy till date. The Chariot festival is usually held on the next day after the holy marriage".³⁰

Poojas and Sevas

Amongst the Hindu Pantheon, even though the three primary responsibilities are assigned to the creator Brahma, the preserver Vishnu and the Destroyer Siva. Among Siva and Vishnu, Lord Vishnu is said to be 'Alankara Priya,' one who owes being dressed up with various embellishments and jewels while Lord Siva is 'Abhishekapriyar' one who is pleased with ablutions. Hence, the rituals in the Meenakshi temple lay a lot of importance on the Poojas for Lord Siva and his consort Goddess 'Meenakshi'. "The temple Poojas fall under three categories, namely 1) Nitya Poojas which are done daily, 2) Maasaabishekam

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(monthly)which are performed once a month and, 3) Visesham or festivals which are celebrated once a year Daily Poojas are offered according to the ‘Aagamashastras’ and are practically the same as they are in many Siva temples. The ritual today is practically what it had been for hundreds of years. The Poojas seem to have been performed six times in the day starting. From the ‘Thiruvanandal pooja’ in the early morning to the ‘Palliyarai pooja at night’. The ‘abhisheka dravyam’ articles included are honey, tender coconuts, two sorts of sandal, plantain fruits, ‘Pacchakarpoora’, Civet, Sugar, Curds, Parimaladravyam or Scents, and Vibhuti.”³¹ The following were used for preparing the ‘naivedhas: black gram, green gram, jaggery, tamarind, salt, pepper, cumin seeds mustard and oil seeds, dry ginger, cardamom and rice. The ‘naivedhyams’ include eatable items made out of rice butter, pulses and cereals. During the day the Nityotsavar, Pallakkusokkar is taken on a procession three times a day round the ‘prakaarams’ of the temple with music and all honours. These Poojas and customs are still observed and continued in the present time.³²

Conclusion

In the Sattur temple, like other temples, there is no practice of ‘Tonsuring’ because coming to the temple and worshipping the God itself, clear away the sins of devotees and they get blessings of the Lord Siva and Goddess Meenakshi. All the festivals are celebrated according to the ‘agama’ rules till this day. Each day is a festival day in the temple.

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